

**PUBLIC POLICIES AS A MECHANISM FOR SOCIAL INTEGRATION:
THE CASE OF VENEZUELAN REFUGEES IN JOÃO PESSOA, FROM
2018 TO 2022**

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ABSTRACT

The municipality of João Pessoa has received, since 2018, Venezuelan refugees through the Acolhida Operation, and to insert them into society, in fact, it is necessary to build public policies so that local integration becomes effective. With this, this article proposes to analyze the construction of public policies implemented in João Pessoa to integrate Venezuelan refugees from 2018 to 2022. of these public policies through the neofunctionalist theory, a theory that strengthens the participation and importance of actors beyond the State. Then, the public policies implemented in João Pessoa will be analyzed, mentioning the bodies and institutions responsible, and how the articulation for this was made. The hypothesis was adopted that the local network was an essential element for public policies to be created and to comply with the general objective, which was proven in the development of the article. To make this study viable, some methodological tools were used, starting with the nature of the basic research, with an explanatory content, through a case study, and with a method of historical procedure. Bibliographic materials were analyzed and as for the method of approach, the work is characterized as inductive. It was concluded, then, the importance of the local network in evoking the preferences/needs of Venezuelan refugees to the appropriate bodies responsible for the public policy agenda. Thus, with the help of the social factor, the State was able to carry out the integration and reception of refugees in João Pessoa.

Initial considerations

The migratory crisis unleashed on a global scale in recent decades has brought serious consequences to the Brazilian State. This is confirmed, according to Cavalcanti (2005, p.1), to the extent that the issue of migration “has continually occupied the main agendas of

governments and international organizations”. In practice, the increase in flows of refugees and displaced populations in the contemporary world has highlighted the difficulties and numerous limitations of countries in ensuring the protection of the Human Rights of refugees and migrants who enter their borders (JUBILUT, 2007).

In the Brazilian context, to ensure basic rights and reformulate the internal legal system, regulations were added to the Brazilian Constitution that deal with social integration, and the rights and duties of refugees, such as the Migration Law (Law n. 13.445/ 2017) and the consequent revocation of the Foreigner Statute (Law n. 6.815/1980). Nevertheless, Brazil has become a destination chosen by migrants seeking refuge, and there is an urgent need for public policies to respond positively to their reception. Based on the scenario described, this article will analyze the participation of the local network in the construction of public policies for Venezuelan refugees in João Pessoa, from 2018 to 2022.

For this, it is necessary to outline specific objectives to guide the course of the research, the first of which is: define refugee and public policies; discuss the construction of public policies through neofunctionalist theory; and list the public policies, referring to the theme of refuge implemented in João Pessoa, in the chosen time frame. To achieve this objective, the guiding question was “How did social actors contribute to the construction of public policies for Venezuelan refugees in João Pessoa?”

We sought to review a topic already discussed in the international relations literature and, therefore, the research was basic, proposing a better understanding of public policies for Venezuelan refugees in João Pessoa, with the aim of generating knowledge on the subject. Second, the research was explanatory, through a case study, the Venezuelans in João Pessoa, bibliographical, as it used documents and reports issued by the participating bodies, with a method of historical procedure. Finally, the method of approach was inductive, starting from the analysis in the capital of Paraíba in order to create models of public policies to be applied in international society.

1. International refugee protection and the conceptualization of public policies

The theme of refugees, that is, of human beings who seek protection in another territory due to the persecution they suffer, is not new. However, according to Jubilut (2007, p.24), the institutionalized protection of these individuals, through a legal institute, only appears around 1950, with the international positivization of the sources of law for refugees.

According to Guerra (2017, p. 68), in 1949, the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) was created, with the purpose of finding lasting solutions to the refugee issue and, resulting from this institutionalization, there are two international legal frameworks to regularize the refuge, they are: the 1951 Convention and the 1967 Protocol, both from the UN. According to these normative instruments, a refugee is defined as any person “[who, fearing persecution for reasons of race, religion, nationality, social group or political opinion, is outside the country of nationality or origin and who does not unable or, owing to such fear, is unwilling to avail himself of the protection of that country.”

According to the *General Paper*, published by UNHCR in November 1982, and as exposed by Liliana Jubilut (2007, p.153), UNHCR has competence to carry out two basic functions (1) to provide the protection of refugees and (2) to promote the implementation of durable solutions to this issue. Both aim to provide the refugee with a life with dignity, assuring them basic rights, through mutual aid from governments and collaboration of civil society.

There are three solutions present in the UNHCR statute (chap.1 §1) and in the Geneva Convention of 1951 (chap.1 article 1, § 6 paragraph d) for the case of forced migrants, they are: repatriation, local integration and resettlement in a third country. The goal is for each one to provide the refugee with a life with dignity, guaranteeing their basic rights and rebuilding their lives. The international protection of refugees ranges from the implementation of national and international norms to their effectiveness in practice, through programs and actions of public policies and reception, protection and local reintegration. (BALBINO, 2018, p.23).

Local integration was the solution found by UNHCR in partnership with the federal government to welcome refugees in Brazilian territory. As a result, each welcoming State needed to develop public policies that would enable the integration, reception and assistance, in fact, of this vulnerable population. But what would these public policies be?

It is important to begin this analysis by conceptualizing the term. Therefore, it should be noted at the outset that several scholars claim that there is not a single and perfect definition of the term “public policy”. As Agum, Riscado and Menezes (2015, p.15) point out, “over the decades the concept has been re-signified”, so some of the most consonant with the object of study will be presented.

Public policy, according to Bucci (2006, p.3), is a governmental action program, “aimed at coordinating the means available to the State and private activities, to achieve socially relevant and politically determined objectives.” Thus, the State would be a central actor through the purposes suggested by society. According to Maria Simões Pires (2001), public policies are

“State responses to society's issues, and are developed in 3 moments: conception, budgeting and implementation”.

One can also mention the idea of Secchi (2009), who defends public policy as a means that allows any social actor to be the protagonist of public policies, provided that the problem to be faced has public characteristics. This multicentric view is adopted on a large scale by several authors due to the attribution of a public nature to actions, which corroborates the involvement of various actors in facing issues relevant to society.

As explained above, the concepts, despite being different, complement each other. This means that the study of public policies implies an analysis of the State's performance, that is, the decisions, measures, programs, strategies, courses of action adopted by the government, both in terms of conception, applicability and consequences in terms of society for which it was conceived.

Thus, migration policies are directly related to political decisions, guided by the State to provide, to a greater or lesser extent, the basic rights to protect the human dignity of refugees, being implemented through public policies. Regardless of their object, policies exert influence on the realization of human rights and serve as an instrument that allows the State to fulfill its obligations.

According to Lussi (2015) migration policies do not only concern the conditions of entry and stay in the country, but also mean a concern for the migrant population, so that they have access to public policies and programs that meet their specific needs, and they are “interdisciplinary, integrated, contextualized, able to recognize and assume the complexity that the subject requires, without simplism” (LUSSI, 2015, p. 142).

According to the guidelines of the Report on Migration in the World (IOM, 2013), one should focus on the consequences of migration for the lives of migrants, understanding that in political debates they have the opportunity to tell their stories, that their participation in the processes takes place actively, placing an emphasis on the dimension of experience, as opposed to the usual interest in socioeconomic dynamics, which would encourage the formulation of public policies that are more compatible with human needs.

the reflection on the construction of public policies based on the neofunctionalist theory will be deepened . The central issue will be aimed at explaining, through theory, the process of building public policy, highlighting key actors and their role in the political process.

2. The construction of public policies for refugees in the light of neofunctionalist theory

In general terms, migration policy moves society as a whole, in addition to being a phenomenon that pervades social, political, geographic, sociological issues, among others. In this perspective, the study of public policies also requires a multidisciplinary analysis, especially due to the interaction between multiple actors involved. As Souza (2006, p.25) states, public policies have repercussions on the economy and society, hence why the theory also needs to explain the interrelationships between the State, politics and society.

As Rocha-Trindade (1995) explains, whatever the reason for the displacement of individuals, “the question of the adjustment of immigrants to the new environment constitutes one of the fundamental aspects related to the migration process”. Or rather, the way in which society, the national legal system, and public policies are received is essential for the success of the process, and João Pessoa, capital of Paraíba, is a national highlight in terms of good practices in reception and promotion the citizenship of refugees (PARAÍBA, 2022).

In this way, we agree with Silva (2022, p.65), when he states that integration begins “in the period of acceptance of the place with the other and vice versa, with constant exchange of efforts, to make the new population is, in fact, welcomed and integrated.” It is from this perspective that the importance of the local network emerges, as support, during the integration process that, Caldeira (2012), claims to be impacted by important actors such as individuals of the same nationality, family/friends, religious organizations, residents' associations, organizations non-governmental organizations, unions, among others.

This means that civil society plays an important role in the local integration process, not just a relationship between refugees and the host government. Lindo (2005) also explains that the integration process requires an interdependence between actors. The dynamics of integration surrounds the host society, institutions, social groups, cultural movements, in constant interaction, thus creating interdependence between these actors. And the participation of national society is the basis of public policies in Brazil. (BRASIL, 2015)

Within this same dynamic, of recognizing the influence of social actors on state actions, neofunctionalist theorists built base concepts, during the 1950s, to try to explain the processes of integration in the international system. The neofunctionalist theory, whose reference names are Joseph Nye, Philippe Schmitter, Leon Lindberg, Robert Keohane and Lawrence Scheinerman, can contribute to understanding the dynamics of society in the construction of public policies.

This theory gives due importance to the participation of parties and interest groups, and how they interfere in the integration processes (KEOHANE, NYE, 1981). Furthermore, it considers that the State is an actor that acts rationally but is understood as a set of groups and internal decision-making processes. For Schmitter (2010), the performance of interest groups depends on understanding the means by which they can voice their preferences, and from that, make the topic relevant to the State. Therefore, neofunctionalism recognizes the existence and importance of agents external to the States, in order to democratize the integration process.

Although the theory explains integration at the macro level, that is, internationally in a relationship between States, the functionalist theory analyzed in the micro form, also favors the practice of cooperation through the decentralization of the State, and the creation of specific institutions for each theme, to the extent that it suggests that institutions play a fundamental role in forming a sense of community [...] “institutionalization is what leads citizens to reinforce their loyalty to a supranational level” (SARFATI, 2006, p. 187).

Therefore, as verified through the neofunctionalist theory, the State actually acts through public policy, but it is important to observe the performance of elites, interest groups, social organizations and political parties. Often, through these groups, social issues are included in the political agenda, as was the case with refugees. Through society, pressure groups, institutions, urgent measures were created to welcome them and think strategically about what could be done in the long term.

Next, government actions and their contributions to addressing the migration issue in João Pessoa, from 2018 to 2022, will be identified. Furthermore, gaps, challenges and obstacles that must be considered to optimize the applicability of these measures with the target audience will be pointed out.

2. Public policies to integrate Venezuelan refugees in João Pessoa (2018-2022)

The arrival of refugees in João Pessoa began due to the creation of the Acolhida Operation, in 2018, as a response to the high number of Venezuelans arriving in Brazil and remaining in the State of Roraima. The operation corresponds to a scheme to “operationalize emergency assistance for the reception of refugees and migrants from Venezuela in a situation of greater vulnerability” (R4V, 2019), and was divided into three main instances: border planning, shelter and interiorization (R4V, 2019).

Even at the beginning of the operation, the highest percentage of interiorization in the Northeast occurred in Paraíba. The state welcomed 144 migrants, representing 4.40% of the total compared to other states in the region (SILVA, 2021, p.44). Currently (July 2022), the State has internalized 958 people, 519 of which in the capital João Pessoa (IOM, 2022).

The role of the State of Paraíba as an institution responsible for guaranteeing legal support and human rights to newly arrived refugees needed to be articulated in 2018, when the first group of Venezuelan refugees arrived in the capital, João Pessoa. In April 2019, eight months after the arrival of the first groups, an initiative by the Escola Superior do Ministério Público da União (ESMPU) in partnership with the Public Ministry of Labor (MPT), the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) and the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF), organized a symposium to exchange experiences and technical information about the Venezuelans who were welcomed.

The Symposium “Networking: Training of Actors Involved in Reception, Integration and Internalization of Refugees and Migrants in Brazil” brought together representatives from various sectors that permeate the reception of refugees, in addition to instructing actors and providing the opportunity for sectors publics came together for greater and better protection. From this, the local reception and integration network in João Pessoa was born.

The Departments of Health, Human Rights, Social Assistance, State University of Paraíba (UEPB), Federal University of Paraíba (UFPB), Public Defender's Office (DPU), Public Ministry of Labor (MPT), Federal Public Ministry (MPF), the National Indian Foundation (FUNAI), representatives of host institutions, church pastoral, among others, are part of this network, which despite not being legally established, articulates and manages to claim its issues with the State.

Thus, the creation of this network enabled professionals in the area of human rights and migration, researchers, professors, among other specialties, to add their knowledge regarding integration and reception, rights and duties, government response, etc. Due to the fact that it was the first experience with a high flow of refugees, public policies aimed at this target audience did not exist, and the support of the local network was essential to identify needs and propose them to the competent bodies. In this way, this network that was formed has been pressuring the municipality of João Pessoa for the creation of a Municipal Law, for example, directed at them, among other measures.

In other words, according to Silva (2021), from several meetings between the interest group interested in making improvements for Venezuelan forced migrants, the eyes of the State

turned to meet the demands of this population. Starting with the attitudes of other actors with a positive example, for example, civil society, these become institutionalized and thus reaching governmental structures capable of generating concrete and de facto changes (RUA, 2013).

Analyzing the practical part, the State Secretariat for Human Development, through an agreement articulated with the State Fund for Combating and Eradicating Poverty (FUNCEP/PB), established a partnership with Archdiocesan Social Action (ASA) and guarantees, since 2020, shelter comprehensive care (food, stay, infrastructure) for indigenous Venezuelan migrants and refugees of the Warao ethnic group, in João Pessoa (PARAÍBA, 2022a).

The Government of Paraíba, through the Secretariat for Women and Human Diversity and the Secretariat of State for Human Development, launched the 'Booklet on the Rights of Migrants' with guidelines for migrants and refugees. The booklet informs about the rights and duties of migrants and government support services in the areas of health, education and violations of rights, such as the State Reference Center for Combating Racism and Religious Intolerance - João Balula, which is already assisting cases of xenophobia and assisting the migrant population in the State (PARAÍBA, 2022b).

In addition, according to the IOM (2022), a partnership was signed between the UN Migration Agency (OIM) and the Pastoral Service of Migrants from the Northeast (SPM/NE) to offer temporary shelter and services for a period of five years. months.

In addition to the shelter, with IOM support, legal support services were offered at the Reference Center of the SPM/NE, in João Pessoa, document regularization, social rent, financial support for opening small enterprises, concession of basic food baskets, validation of diplomas, referrals to public services in the area of health, education, social assistance, work and income (IOM, 2022).

An agreement was signed between the State Secretariat for Human Development (SEDH) and the Archdiocesan Social Action (ASA/PB) carried out with resources from the State Fund for Combating and Eradicating Poverty in the State of Paraíba (Funcep), in order to provide the full shelter (food, accommodation, cleaning materials and others) of Waraos indigenous Venezuelan migrants (PARAÍBA, 2022c).

The Municipal Health Secretariat (SMS) made available an Odontomóvel, a vehicle equipped to carry out various dental services to assist Venezuelans sheltered in João Pessoa, after a survey to draw the epidemiological profile in order to elaborate a service flow in the municipal network to the group. (CITY HALL OF JOÃO PESSOA, 2020a)

In March 2020, during the COVID-19 pandemic, some families had health problems and according to the MPF, bank accounts were opened for this population, to allow the payment of government aid (MPF, 2020a). In addition, symptomatic refugees were tested, and those who tested positive were isolated, where they received food and daily monitoring to monitor the evolution of symptoms (MPF, 2020b).

In April 2020, the Leite Fraterno campaign took place, which made available around 4,000 liters of milk distributed in the large cities of Paraíba, in addition to hygiene kits for families in vulnerable situations, including the Warao indigenous people (MPF, 2020c).

There was also the Natal Solidário 2020 campaign by the Department of Roads in Paraíba, which distributed twenty-seven basic food baskets to families in the Valentina de Figueiredo neighborhood, including Venezuelan refugees. (DER, 2020)

On the subject of health, a joint effort was carried out with professionals from the Integrated Family Health Unit “Saúde e Vida”, from the João Pessoa City Hall (PMJP), who carried out health and monitoring actions for the group of indigenous Venezuelans housed at the Carmelita Pereira School Gomes. During the action, rapid tests for HIV/AIDS, hepatitis and blood glucose were carried out with the refugees. The activity is integrated with other PMJP secretariats, such as the Social Development Secretariat (SEDES) and the Education Secretariat (SEDEC). (CITY HALL OF JOÃO PESSOA, 2020b)

The project 'João Pessoa – inclusive and diverse city'. This is a Technical Cooperation between the Municipality and the Inter-American Development Bank (IDB) and involves the Executing Unit of the Sustainable João Pessoa Program, the Extraordinary Secretariat for Public Policies for Women (SEPPM) and the Secretariat for Urban Security and Citizenship (SEMUSB), which aims to train public agents to prevent and deal with violence, discrimination and phobias suffered by the most vulnerable populations, including refugees. (CITY HALL OF JOÃO PESSOA, 2022c)

Analyzing the role of each institution that makes up the S System (SESC, SENAC, SENAI), Pacífico and Mendonça (2010) show that the Social Service of Commerce (SESC) offers training programs to refugees in partnership with the Archdiocesan Worker Center (CET). The National Service for Industrial Learning (SENAI) offers “professional courses for training, qualification, improvement, specialization and intensive training of refugees” (PACÍFICO; MENDONÇA, 2010, p. 176).

In addition to these activities, UNHCR (sd) works so that Venezuelan refugees can participate in the social programs already established in João Pessoa, which has in fact been

consolidated. By registering at the Social Assistance Reference Center (CRAS), they were able to receive the family allowance, Brazil aid, low-income discount on energy bills (Social Tariff), Projovem, among others.

Society in this case was fundamental. As already mentioned, the formation of the local network is the basis for educational, health, social, safety, work, among others, demands to be taken to the responsible bodies and enter the list of government agendas. The symposium held through the Federal Public Prosecutor's Office was essential to bring together those interested in the subject, professionals who know the particularities of forced migration, and leaders of various institutions and social organizations. It is noteworthy here that the symposium only brought together those interested, but the local network already existed since the arrival of the first group of Venezuelans.

With this, the process of welcoming refugees in João Pessoa is positively punctuated. The measures implemented by the State government, City Hall, and its various thematic bodies, were efficient in seeking to ensure social well-being and the guarantee of human rights. But again, this would not have happened without the pressure groups, civil society, NGOs, the Church, the support network.

Final considerations

The arrival of Venezuelan refugees in the municipality of João Pessoa exemplifies a concrete situation of the importance of public policies, and also helps in the analysis of the responsibilities and attributions of the public power in Brazil regarding the knowledge of the rights, political participation and emancipation of the resident refugees in Brazilian territory . In fact, as analyzed, cooperation between the State, city hall, institutions, civil society, leaders, NGOs, was a contributing factor for the successful reception of refugees.

The participation of different actors in issues in which the State has final decision-making power has been studied since 1950. The neofunctionalist theory contributed to the analysis as it highlighted important points in this relationship of decentralization and cooperation. Through it, it can be confirmed that the organization of the local network, even at the beginning of the arrival of the groups, was a decisive factor in guiding the articulation between the institutions. Bringing together different technical bodies, policy agents, refugees and those interested in the area was a positive experience and resulted in the organization of the main agendas that needed answers from the State.

The matter of public policies was analyzed in general, but it can be seen that several areas, such as health, social assistance, education, economy, were punctuated and had their value in view of the needs of the population. Even though it did not completely contemplate public policies, the municipality of João Pessoa assertively responded to the demands of society.

It is suggested as a topic for future research, the impacts of these policies on refugees. Investigating whether the vast majority of them managed to participate, or whether they were not even aware of them, is something to be punctuated when analyzing the effectiveness of social integration and humanitarian reception.

Finally, the organization of the local network in João Pessoa, together with the competent bodies, managed to summarize the needs, take them to the competent authorities so that they could be included in the public policy agenda and then come to be implemented. Thus, it is possible to guarantee at least the minimum reception to those who needed it so much.

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